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Title: Quantification of inflammatory proteins in DBS using UHPLC/MS**Date: 4.1.2023****Version: version 1****Author: Veronika Vidová****Checked: Kateřina Coufalíková****Summary:**

Inflammation is a defense response to stimulus, for example, infection, tissue damage, or cancer development, that the human body performs to attain homeostasis. The quantification of selected highly conserved APPs, such as C-reactive protein (CRP), α -1 antitrypsin (A1AT), serum amyloid A (SAA), and α -1-acid glycoprotein (A1AG), including relevant isoforms and adaptive immunity effectors (i.e., antibodies) presumably allows for stratification among specific types of inflammation and for differentiation between physiological and pathological responses.

Table with analyzed proteins and the targeted peptides

Accession number	Gene Name	Protein Name	Protein Acronym UniProt Entry Name	Target Peptide
P0DJ18	SAA1	Serum amyloid A1	SAA1	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR
P0DJ18/P0DJ19	SAA1/2	Serum amyloid A1 and A2	SAA1/2	SFFSFLGEAFDGR GAEDSLADQAANK
P0DJ19-1	SAA2-1	Serum amyloid A2 Isoform 1	SAA2-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK GPGGAWAAEVISNAR
P35542	SAA4	Serum amyloid A4	SAA4	FRPDGLPK EALQGVGDMGR
P01876	IGHA1	Immunoglobulin heavy constant alpha 1	IGHA1	TPLTATLSK
P02763	ORM1	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 1	A1AG1	NWGLSVYADKPETTK
P19652	ORM2	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 2	A1AG2	SDVMYTDWK TLMFGSYLDDEK
P01009-1	SERPINA1	Alpha-1-antitrypsin Isoform 1	A1AT-1	AVLTIDEK
P02741	CRP	C-reactive protein	CRP	ESDTSYVSLK

Safety information

- DBS samples are classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.

Overview of reagents

- ammonium bicarbonate buffer (ABB), acetic acid, acetonitrile (ACN) LC-MS grade, formic acid (FA) LC-MS grade, milliQ

Equipment

- 10 µL multichannel, 100 µL multichannel pipettes & 1000 µL automatic pipette
- Orbital shaker incubator
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates
- pH meter
- 96-well plates SPE manifold with pump

Consumables & glassware

- 50 mL Falcon screw cap plastic vials
- 700 µL 96-and 1500 µL well plates with silicone sealing
- 10 µL, 100 µL & 1 mL tips
- 500 µL Eppendorf tubes
- 96 well plate SPE HLB PRIME 30 mg
- parafilm

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

Protein extraction buffer

- 50 mM ABB (40 mg/10 mL in milliQ)
- For 40 mL of solution, weigh 160 mg ABB into 50 mL screw plastic vial
- Add 40 mL of milliQ
- Solution should have pH=7.8 (measure with pH meter)

Solution can be kept for up to 7 days at 4°C

Trypsin solution

- As described in trypsin standard manual, dissolve 100 µg lyophilized trypsin in 100 µL of 50 mM acetic acid.

SPE solutions

- 2 % FA, (pH<3)
- 50 % ACN with 2 % FA, (pH<3)
- 5 % ACN with 0.1 % FA

Reagents for mobile phase preparation

- ACN, LC-MS grade
- FA, LC-MS grade
- milliQ water

Standard preparation

- to prepare 1 mL of Peptide standard mixture mix volumes of 10 µM peptide standard listed in Table 1 and 677.5 µL of 5% ACN.

Table 1: Standard peptide mix volumes and concentrations

Protein Acronym	Protein Accession Number	Sequence	Concentration of peptide [nM]	Volume of 10 µM standard [µl]
SAA1	P0DJI8	H-FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWG-R*-Qtag	100	10
SAA1/2	P0DJI8/P0DJI9	H-SFFSFLGEAFDGA-R*-Qtag	400	40
	P0DJI9-1	H-LTGHGAEDSLADQAAN-K*-Qtag	100	10
SAA2-1	P0DJI9-1	H-GAEDSLADQAAN-K*-Qtag	100	10
	P0DJI9-1	H-GPGGAWAAEVISNA-R*-Qtag	250	25
SAA4	P35542	H-FRPDGLP-K*-Qtag	100	10
	P35542	H-EALQGVGDMG-R*-Qtag	100	10
IGHA1	P01876	H-TPLTATLS-K*-Qtag	1000	100
A1AG1	P02763	H-NWGLSVYADKPETT-K*-Qtag	600	60
A1AG2	P19652	H-SDVMYTDW-K*-Qtag	200	20
	P19652	H-TLMFGSYLDDE-K*-Qtag	200	20
A1AT-1	P01009-1	H-AVLTIDE-K*-Qtag	25	2.5
CRP	P02741	H-ESDTSYVSL-K*-Qtag	50	5

Sample preparation

Protein extraction

1. Take out DBS from -80 °C freezer and leave at room temperature for 20 min
2. Cut the 3 mm spot from DBS
3. Place the DBS spot into a 500 µL tube or 1500 µL microplate and add 150 µL of extraction buffer
4. Place onto the shaker and shake 200 RPM for 60 min at room temperature
5. Take 5 µL of extract for total protein analysis using BCA kit (extract needs to be diluted 100x)
6. Take 30 µL of extract for target protein analysis and place into a new 500 µL vial or deep well plate

Trypsin digestion

7. Add 10 µL standard peptide mixture and then 3 µL of trypsin solution (1µg/µL)
8. Close vials properly and seal with parafilm or seal microplate with silicone seal
9. Place into a heat shaker and shake at 200 RPM for 17 hours at 37 °C
10. Spin down for 30 s for 3000 x g
11. Stop digestion adding 200 µL of 2% FA

SPE in 96-well microplate format

12. Load sample solution into a SPE well and turn vacuum on to elute solution into waste
13. Wash sample with 300 µL of 2% FA
14. Elute peptides with 200 µL 50 % ACN with 2 % FA into a 700 µL microplate with V bottom
15. Dry out the sample in speedvac at 40 °C for 3h
16. Dissolve in 30 µL 5 % ACN with 0.1 % FA
17. Vortex properly
18. Analyze using UHPLC/MS or place into a freezer -20 °C

Mobile phase preparation

- Mobile phase A: 0.1 % FA in milliQ water

- Mobile phase B: 95 % ACN with 0.1 % FA

LC-QQQ analysis

19. Clean the source and nebulizer before measurement
20. Check solvent for needle rinsing
21. Check solvent for seals rinsing
22. Prepare mobile phase
23. Input sequence
24. Start LC-QQQ analysis run
25. Check initial blanks and QC

NOTE: If problems, stop run, cap samples and store at -20°C whilst troubleshooting.

NOTE: Measure with every sample set:

- Instrument blank (Mobile phase A)
- QC (standard peptide mix)
- Calibration curve in matrix: prepare pool of meconium/stool extracts → spike Labeled standard mix (use 6 different concentration) → measure 6 calibration points with 3 - 6 replicates (6 replicates for LOD, LOQ determination)

LC-QQQ sequence setup

1. Clean blank
2. Clean blank
3. QC
4. Samples 1-3
5. Instrument blank
6. Sample 4-6
7. Instrument blank
8. Sample 7-9 ...

NOTE: measure Instrument blank after every 3 samples

NOTE: measure QC with every 30 samples

9. Calibration
10. End with Instrument blank, QC and 2 x Clean blank
11. Run samples with dSRM assay as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. SRM assay library for positive ion detection mode

Protein Accession Number	Peptide light/heavy	Precursor Ion	Product Ion	Ion Name
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.28	733.45	y7
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.28	519.31	y5
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.28	415.75	y8
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.28	312.19	b3
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.28	741.46	y7
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.28	527.33	y5
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.28	419.76	y8
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.28	312.19	b3
P01009-1	AVLTIDEK.light	444.76	718.40	y6
P01009-1	AVLTIDEK.light	444.76	605.31	y5
P01009-1	AVLTIDEK.light	444.76	284.20	b3
P01009-1	AVLTIDEK.heavy	448.76	726.41	y6
P01009-1	AVLTIDEK.heavy	448.76	613.33	y5
P01009-1	AVLTIDEK.heavy	448.76	284.20	b3
P02741	ESDTSYVSLK.light	564.77	696.39	y6
P02741	ESDTSYVSLK.light	564.77	609.36	y5
P02741	ESDTSYVSLK.light	564.77	347.23	y3
P02741	ESDTSYVSLK.heavy	568.78	704.41	y6
P02741	ESDTSYVSLK.heavy	568.78	617.37	y5
P02741	ESDTSYVSLK.heavy	568.78	355.24	y3
P02763	NWGLSVYADKPETTK.light	570.29	704.87	y13
P02763	NWGLSVYADKPETTK.light	570.29	619.82	y11
P02763	NWGLSVYADKPETTK.light	570.29	301.13	b2
P02763	NWGLSVYADKPETTK.heavy	572.96	708.88	y13
P02763	NWGLSVYADKPETTK.heavy	572.96	623.82	y11
P02763	NWGLSVYADKPETTK.heavy	572.96	301.13	b2
PODJI8/PODJI9	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR.light	775.87	935.46	y9
PODJI8/PODJI9	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR.light	775.87	822.37	y8
PODJI8/PODJI9	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR.light	775.87	235.11	b4
PODJI8/PODJI9	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR.heavy	780.87	945.47	y9
PODJI8/PODJI9	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR.heavy	780.87	832.38	y8
PODJI8/PODJI9	SFFSFLGEAFDGAR.heavy	780.87	235.11	b4
PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.light	726.66	732.34	y6
PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.light	726.66	661.31	y5
PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.light	726.66	418.22	y3

PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.light	726.66	232.14	y2
PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.heavy	730.00	742.35	y6
PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.heavy	730.00	671.31	y5
PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.heavy	730.00	428.23	y3
PODJI8	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR.heavy	730.00	242.15	y2
PODJI9-1	GPGGAWAAEVISNAR.light	728.37	930.50	y9
PODJI9-1	GPGGAWAAEVISNAR.light	728.37	859.46	y8
PODJI9-1	GPGGAWAAEVISNAR.light	728.37	340.16	b5
PODJI9-1	GPGGAWAAEVISNAR.heavy	733.37	940.51	y9
PODJI9-1	GPGGAWAAEVISNAR.heavy	733.37	869.47	y8
PODJI9-1	GPGGAWAAEVISNAR.heavy	733.37	340.16	b5
PODJI9-1	GAEDSLADQAANK.light	645.30	717.35	y7
PODJI9-1	GAEDSLADQAANK.light	645.30	646.32	y6
PODJI9-1	GAEDSLADQAANK.light	645.30	261.16	y2
PODJI9-1	GAEDSLADQAANK.heavy	649.31	725.37	y7
PODJI9-1	GAEDSLADQAANK.heavy	649.31	654.33	y6
PODJI9-1	GAEDSLADQAANK.heavy	649.31	269.17	y2
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.light	566.61	717.35	y7
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.light	566.61	646.32	y6
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.light	566.61	215.14	b2
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.light	566.61	537.28	b6
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.heavy	569.28	725.37	y7
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.heavy	569.28	654.33	y6
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.heavy	569.28	215.14	b2
PODJI9-1	LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK.heavy	569.28	537.28	b6
P19652	SDVMYTDWK.light	572.75	843.37	y6
P19652	SDVMYTDWK.light	572.75	712.33	y5
P19652	SDVMYTDWK.light	572.75	302.13	b3
P19652	SDVMYTDWK.heavy	576.76	851.38	y6
P19652	SDVMYTDWK.heavy	576.76	720.34	y5
P19652	SDVMYTDWK.heavy	576.76	302.13	b3
P19652	TLMFGSYLDDEK.light	709.83	1073.48	y9
P19652	TLMFGSYLDDEK.light	709.83	926.41	y8
P19652	TLMFGSYLDDEK.light	709.83	215.14	b2
P19652	TLMFGSYLDDEK.heavy	713.84	1081.49	y9
P19652	TLMFGSYLDDEK.heavy	713.84	934.42	y8
P19652	TLMFGSYLDDEK.heavy	713.84	215.14	b2
P35542	EALQGVGDMGR.light	566.77	691.32	y7
P35542	EALQGVGDMGR.light	566.77	535.23	y5
P35542	EALQGVGDMGR.light	566.77	201.09	b2
P35542	EALQGVGDMGR.heavy	571.78	701.33	y7
P35542	EALQGVGDMGR.heavy	571.78	545.24	y5
P35542	EALQGVGDMGR.heavy	571.78	201.09	b2

P35542	FRPDGLPK.light	310.51	244.17	y2
P35542	FRPDGLPK.light	310.51	313.68	y6
P35542	FRPDGLPK.light	310.51	573.28	b5
P35542	FRPDGLPK.heavy	313.18	252.18	y2
P35542	FRPDGLPK.heavy	313.18	317.69	y6
P35542	FRPDGLPK.heavy	313.18	573.28	b5

SRM protein quantitative/semiquantitative evaluation

Results are recalculated to protein concentration based on the molecular weight in volume of blood (one DBS punch contain 3 µL of blood).

LC-QQQ method setup

Multisampler		
Injection volume	5.00 µL	
Needle Wash	Multi-wash	
Stoptime	As Pump/No Limit	
Posttime	Off	
Advanced		
Sampling Speed	Draw Speed	100 µL/min
	Eject Speed	100 µL/min
	Wait Time After Draw	0 s
Needle Height Position	Offset	-0.4 mm
	Use Vial/Well Bottom Sensing	Yes
High Throughput	Sample Flush-Out Factor	5
	Injection Valve to Bypass for Delay Volume Reduction	No
	Enable Overlapped Injection	No

Binary Pump				
Flow	0.300 mL/min			
Solvents	A	95%	0.1 % FA	
	B	5%	95 % ACN with 0.1 % FA	
Pressure Limits	Min	0 bar		
	Max	1200 bar		
Stoptime	35 min			
Posttime	30 s			
Advanced				
Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]	Flow [%]	Max. Pressure Limit [bar]
0	95	5	0.3	1200
25	30	70		
25.3	5	95		
30	5	95		
31	95	5		
35	95	5		

Column Comp.	
Advanced	
Column temperature	40 °C
Enable Analysis	When front door open
	When temperature is within ± 0.8 °C
Valve Position/Column After Run	Do not switch

QQQ		
Source		
Source parameters		
Gas Temp:	200 °C	
Gas Flow:	18 l/min	
Nebulizer:	25 psi	
Sheath Gas Temp:	350 °C	
Sheath Gas Flow:	12 l/min	
Capillary:	3500 V (Positive)	3000 V (Negative)
Nozzle Voltage:	500 V (Positive)	1500 V (Negative)
iFunnel parameters		
High Pressure RF	150 V (Positive)	90 V (Negative)
Low Pressure RF	60 V (Positive)	60 V (Negative)

Chromatogram					
Stop Time	No limit/As Pump				
Ion source	AJS ESI				
Time filtering	Peak width	0.05 min			
Time segments					
#	Start Time	Scan Type	Div Valve	Delta EMV (+)	Delta EMV (-)
1	0	dynamicMRM	To waste	0	0
2	2	dynamicMRM	To MS	0	0
3	27	dynamicMRM	To waste	0	0